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Solid oxide electrolyze cells prototype based on self-produced electrode supported tape cast cells and powder metallurgy interconnects: The CO₂Sin Project

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Abstract

The present work presents the advances on the development of a solid oxide electrolyze (SOE) prototype based on the own production of electrode supported tape cast cells combined with powder metallurgy interconnects (PM-IC). This progress has been developed by a consortium of two companies FAE producing the fuel electrode supported cells and AMES producing the PM-IC. IREC, as a research center is in charge of the testing and validating of the developed stacks. Single repetition units (SRU) and sub-stacks have been already produced and recently tested achieving 300 mA/cm² of injected current density at 1.4V under steam electrolysis and coelectrolysis modes. A SOEC prototype has been build and validated with 1kW commercial stacks. This prototype has been tested on a real industrial environment by coupling to a water treatment plant. As water is converted into hydrogen, values of 80% conversion have been obtained under a total injected current of 18 A and a voltage of 42 V, which corresponds to a production of more than 180L/h of hydrogen for SOEC prototype validation with the commercial stack coupled to the CO₂ outstream of the digesters of a water treatment plant to produce synthetic methane.

All these activities have been carried out under the frame of the CO₂SIN project (EU-RIS3-COMRDI15-1-0037-06).

Introduction

Electrolyser devices are fundamentally based on SOFC technology operating in reverse mode. In an electrolyser stack, the cells determine the final performance, and therefore, a strong emphasis on increasing the cell quality should be carried out. The improvement of cell performance may be tackled on three different levels: i) materials selection, ii) microstructure of the electrodes, and iii) quality and adhesion of the interfaces [1,2]. In addition, the stability of used materials becomes very important for the good operation and durability of the SOFC systems. SOEC cells are commonly derived from cells developed for SOFC operation. In general, such cells can stably operate in SOEC mode with no or minor modifications. However, an oxygen electrode that works stably in SOFC mode may experience rapid performance decay in electrolysis mode due to electrode delamination caused by oxygen evolution at the oxygen electrode/electrolyte interface [3].

This work presents the advances on the development of solid oxide electrolysis fuel electrode supported tape cast cells, the production of powder metallurgy based interconnects (PM-IC) and the preliminary validation of the balance of plant of a 1kW electrolyze prototype based on the own technology. The manufactured SOEC prototype was validated with a commercial 1kW stacks and tested on a real industrial environment by coupled with the CO₂ rich biogas outstream of the digesters of an industrial water treatment plant to produce synthetic methane. All these activities have been carried out under the frame of the CO₂SIN project (EU-RIS3- COMRD115-1-0037-06)

1. Scientific Approach

The main research topics here presented are the design, manufacturing and validation of components to fabricate a stack based on fuel electrode supported (FES) solid oxide cells and PM interconnects, and the development of the balance of plant and the validation of an electrolyzer prototype based on SOEC technology.

In this work, fuel electrode supported solid oxide cells made using aqueous-based tape casting and screen-printing techniques were fabricated for fuel cell (SOFC) and electrolysis (SOEC) modes by FAE Company. Afterwards, cells of 36 cm² of active area were produced and tested in Single Repeating Unit (SRUs) and short-stack configurations SOEC (steam electrolysis) and Co-SOEC (steam and CO₂ co-electrolysis) modes, offering remarkable performance results. Metallic interconnects made have been obtained by means of powder metallurgy technology (PM-IC) from ferritic stainless steels powders at AMES Company with 36 cm² of active area and tested in SRU at 750°C in SOEC mode.

New developments have been incorporated in the FES cells production to obtain a co-sintered half cell using aqueous-based tape casting to finally deposit the CGO barrier layer and LSCF oxygen electrode by screen printing techniques at industrial scale at FAE Company. PM-IC have been obtained by means of powder metallurgy technology from ferritic stainless steels powders at AMES Company. Fabricated cells have been structurally and electrochemically characterised under electrolysis (SOEC) and coelectrolysis (CO-SOEC) modes. Fuel electrode supported solid oxide cells and metallic interconnect, have been tested in single repeating unit (SRU) offering remarkable performance results. The Area Specific Resistance (ASR) values were measured with four-probe method under an isothermal condition at 770°C. ASR was calculated using Ohm's law from the slope of the curve, obtained by plotting the measured voltage as a function of the applied current normalized by area.

Another major objective of this study was the design, construction and validation with a commercial 1 kW stack tested on a real industrial environment and the development of the required balance of plant. The SOEC prototype is being installed to be operated under electrolysis and co-electrolysis mode coupled to the biogas out stream of an industrial water treatment plant [5].

The manufacturing of the electrolyzer prototype as well as its components (cell and interconnector) are part of the CO₂SIN project (fig.1) which aims to validate the production of renewable synthetic natural gas in a water treatment plant based in the Barcelona area. This project considers two types of electrolysis technologies for hydrogen generation: 37 kW of a commercial alkaline electrolyzer that operates at pressure (12 Bar) and the prototype solid oxide electrolysis system (SOEC) with higher efficiency to operate in electrolysis and coelectrolysis mode that is part of this study. The project also includes a biogas cleaning unit and a catalytic methanization reactor.

Fig. 1: Scheme of the CO₂SIN project

2. Experimental procedure

Nickel-yttria-stabilized zirconia (Ni-YSZ) fuel electrode supported solid oxide cells are composed of a Ni-YSZ support and fuel functional layer (FFL), a dense YSZ electrolyte, a CGO barrier layer and a LSCF cathode. The half cells that includes the Ni-YSZ support, the FFL and electrolyte were fabricated by aqueous multi-layered tape-casting process at industrial scale in FAE Company. YSZ (8% Y₂O₃-ZrO₂ by Kceracell), NiO (Kceracell) and a pore former (Sigma-Aldrich) were used to prepare FES, FFL and electrolyte. PEG 400, Duramax B1000 and Dolapix PC75 were employed as a plasticizer, binder and dispersant, respectively and water as a solvent. The YSZ slurry ratio in terms of powder:solvent:binder:plastizer:dispersant was 23:5:4:1:1. FFL slurry was prepared following the same approach, mixing NiO:YSZ in a 1:1 ratio by ball milling and the slurries prepared as YSZ slurries. FES slurry was prepared by a mixture of NiO:YSZ:PMMA (as pore former) in a 4:4:1 ratio by ball milling and the slurries prepared as YSZ and FFL ones. The half-cells were subsequently co-sintered at >1300°C presenting an area of 8 x 8 cm² and a total thickness around 600 μm. Afterwards, a cation diffusion barrier layer CGO (Gd_{0.2}Ce_{0.8}O₂) was deposited by scree-printing and sintered at >1200°C. Finally, a LSCF (La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O₃ oxygen electrode was deposited by screen-printing and subsequently sintered (Fig. 2 a)) [6]. Cells were tested in the IREC test bench equipped with a DC power supply and electronic loads that allowed reversible operation able to measure either single cells or stacks.

In this work the Interconnect has produced from a 22%wt Cr, 0.6%wt Mn, 1%wt Mo, Fe rest alloy manufactured by Epson Atmix Corporation from Japan which was compacted in a die at a pressure of 3 Tm/cm². Ferritic stainless steel (FSS) are good candidates as metallic interconnects in SOC technology at high temperatures (800°C) as they offer simultaneously high electronic conductivity, high thermal conductivity, gas tightness and thermal expansion coefficient matching that other stack components [7]. P/M interconnects has some advantages over traditional manufactures (casting-rolling-forging route) such as near-net shape production, fast and high production rates, elimination and reduction of machining step and scrap material [8]. After a compacting process the samples were thermally treated in a continuous belt furnace under a reducing atmosphere at 1250°C to 300 seconds/drawer has been performed to sinter the final piece (8 x 8 cm²). In the present case, the samples fabricated to test the interconnect functionality and needs, have a continuous peaks and valley geometry. In the sintered interconnect (fig. 2 b)), a final density of 7.32 g/cm³ has been achieved for all the fabricated pieces. This final density, represents a 95% of the same chemical composition that the solid with a 29% in dimensional change (shrinkage) due to thermic process. In order to minimise the Cr-poisoning effect, a protective (Mn,Co)₃O₄ spinel coatings has been applied on the sintered interconnect by roll painting of a commercial powder suspension in terpineol (Sigma-Aldrich) with sintering cycles (reduction and oxidation treatment) for the coating sintering. The ASR values of interconnectors were measured with four-probe method under an isothermal condition at 770°C for 500h in air for one side and a mix of 90% N₂/10% H₂ on the other side. Heating and cooling rates were set to 1°C/min to reproduce the operating conditions for solid oxide cell operations. Area Specific Resistance (ASR) was calculated using Ohm's law from the slope of the curve, obtained by plotting the measured voltage as a function of the applied current (from -5 A to 5 A) normalized by area.

Fig 2: a) ASC manufactured at FAE, b) PM-IC manufactured at AMES and c) SRU components

The cells are assembled into single repeating unit (SRU) to build up a stack [2,7]. A single repeating unit consisting on a cell and two interconnectors, glass sealing, Ni foam at the fuel electrode and Ag mesh.

The high temperature electrolyze prototype (Fig.3) is completely designed and developed in Spain through the collaboration of research centers (IREC, UPC) and companies (FAE, AMES). The main components of the prototype are the oven or heating system, the mass flow controller and meter system for fuel gas (H₂O or CO₂) and waste or product gases (air, oxygen and H₂), the controlled evaporator mixer (CEM) to obtain the water vapor. The control and program system as well as the planning of the various working methods, the possible actions in case of emergency and the continuous data collection and graphing

has been designed, programmed and assembled internally at AMES. The SOEC prototype was validated with a commercial 1kW stacks and tested on a real industrial environment by coupling to an industrial water treatment plant. The commercial stack (SOFCMAN company) is composed by 30-cell planar 8 x 8 cm² cathode supported cells made with Ni-YSZ, YSZ electrolyte, CGO barrier layer and LSCF-CGO oxygen electrodes with a total active area of 1900 cm² and has been tested as water electrolyser at 750°C on the water treatment plant.

Fig. 3: SOEC prototype on the water treatment plant

3. Results

SRU electrochemical test

Developed cell were assembled in SRU between two PM-IC and one cell with ceramic sealing, Ni foam and Ag mesh in order to ensure de current contact and to facility the assembly. Figure 4 shows the I-V polarization curve for the SRU under SOEC and Co-SOEC mode at 750°C. The presented I-V curves have been obtained under 50 NmL·min⁻¹·cm⁻² of 90/10 H₂O/H₂ for the SOEC measurement and 65/25/10 H₂O/CO₂/H₂ for the Co-SOEC measurement at the fuel electrode, and 150 NmL·min⁻¹·cm⁻² of synthetic air at the oxygen electrode. The SRU present the expected OCV (>1.1) and a maximum injected current density around 0.3A/cm² for both cases at 1.4V.

Fig. 4: I-V polarization curve of SRU under SOEC and Co-SOEC mode for a single fuel electrode cell and two PM interconnector SRU

SRU Characterization after testing

The SRU was characterized by EDS-SEM after 150h of tests in order to find Cr poisoning to due to the high chromium content of the IC-PM (figure 5 a) and to verify the MnCo protective barrier layer functionality. The line scan analysis of the cell confirms that after 150 h of testing there is no chromium poisoning on the cell showing the desired stability at high temperatures.

Fig. 5: a) SEM image and b) chemical compounds mapping of SRU cross-section tested and the different elemental compositional EDS maps of c) oxygen, d) nickel, e)Iron, f)chromium, g) cobalt.

SOEC Prototype validation in water treatment plant

The SOEC prototype was validated in the laboratory with a commercial 1kW stacks at 750°C under 80% of FU (atmosphere condition shows in the figure 6). This test confirms that the designed balance of plant of the prototype was working at the operation conditions of 750°C achieving 80% of steam conversion under an injected current of 32A and a voltage of 39 V that correspond to 400L/h of hydrogen in SOEC mode.

Fig. 6: I-V polarization curve of 1 kW commercial stack at SOEC prototype at 750°C

SOEC Prototype tested

Once the electrolyze prototype was coupled to the water treatment plant, its behavior was validated in electrolysis mode for the generation of H₂ in the plant. Different types of operation regime were studied. Focusing on the analysis of the effect of variable current injection with I-V curves made at 750°C in steam electrolysis mode (Fig.7). Values of 80% conversion have been obtained under a current of 18 A and a voltage of 42 V, showing a lower performance than the obtained on the laboratory tests. Further experiments are needed to optimize the operation on the real industrial environment.

Fig. 7 – I-V polarization curve in electrolysis obtained in the water treatment plant at 750°C

4.-Conclusions

Functional fuel electrode supported tape cast cells and coated powder metallurgy based interconnects (PM-IC) have been obtained and tested as SRU for solid state electrolyzer (SOEC) systems. The coating applied to the interconnector after 150h of testing at 770°C demonstrates its effectiveness as a barrier to chrome, preventing cell poisoning.

The 1kW electrolyze prototype has been designed, built and validated with a commercial stack. 32A have been injected at 39 V with a commercial stack (1kW) in the laboratory tests while a lower performance of 18A at 41V has been obtained on the validation of the integrated prototype at the water treatment plan.

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